

Table 1. Primary antibodies used

Peptide/protein target	Antigen sequence	Name of antibody	Method	Manufacturer, catalog No.	Species raised in; monoclonal or polyclonal	Dilution used	References
phosphatase and tensin homologue deleted on chromosome ten (PTEN)	Carboxy-terminal sequence of human PTEN	PTEN (26H9)	IF	Cell Signaling, 9556S	Mouse; monoclonal	1:100	[42, 57, 58]
green fluorescent protein (GFP)	Purified recombinant GFP emulsified in Freund's adjuvant	Anti-GFP (green fluorescent protein)	IF	AVES, GFP-1010	Chicken; polyclonal	1: 1000	
kisspeptin	N terminus of the full-length mouse KISS1 protein	Anti-kisspeptin	WB	Abcam, ab19028	Rabbit; polyclonal	2 ug/mL	[63, 64]
kisspeptin	Ten amino acid C-terminal of murine kisspeptin (residues 43–52)	Anti-kisspeptin Batch #566	IF/IHC	Alain Caraty, Institute National de la Recherche Agronomique, Paris, France	Rabbit; polyclonal	1:10,000	[55, 56]

β -actin	Amino-terminus of human β -actin	β -actin	WB	Cell Signaling; 13E5	Rabbit; monoclonal	1:1000	
P70 S6 kinase	Residues surrounding (Ser235 and Ser236)	Phospho-S6 Ribosomal protein	IF	Cell signaling, 2211S	Rabbit; polyclonal	1: 200	[59, 60]

A.

B.

Supp. Fig. 1. (A) Representative photomicrographs of adult WT and Kiss-PTEN KO testicular tissue (cross-section) showing normal seminiferous tubules and spermatogonic cells (Sg, spermatogonia; Sz, spermatozoa). (B) Representative photomicrographs of adult WT and Kiss-PTEN KO ovaries (CL, corpus luteum). Scale bars: (A) = 50 μm ; (B) = 200 μm .

Supp. Fig. 3. Immunoblots showing detection of β -actin and kisspeptin protein (red arrow points to expected band at 15 kDa) in the POA and MBH of WT and Kiss-PTEN KO mice that were fed or fasted for 48 hours. Non-specific bands are enclosed in brackets. MW, molecular weight markers.

Supp. Fig. 2. (A) Representative immunofluorescent images of Kiss-GFP+ neurons (green), and Pten (red) in the AVPV with right panels showing representative images omitting the primary antibodies. (B) Representative immunofluorescent images of Kiss-GFP+ neurons (green), and pS6 (red), in the AVPV with right panels showing representative images omitting the primary antibodies. (C) Representative images of AVPV and ARC kisspeptin-ir with right panels showing representative images omitting the primary antibody.